

X-Ray, Thermal and Spectroscopic Studies of Nickel and Manganese Palmitates

K. N. MEHROTRA*, POONAM RAJWANSHI, SMITA MISRA and M. K. RAWAT

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Basic Sciences, Agra University, Khandari, Agra-282 002

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The physicochemical characteristics of metal soaps can be controlled upto an extent by the method and conditions of their preparation and so the studies of metal soaps are of significance for their uses in various industries. The present work deals with the X-ray, thermal and spectroscopic studies of Ni and Mn palmitates in solid state and in solutions.

Results and Discussion

X-Ray diffraction analysis : The appearance of diffractions upto 28th and 24th order for Ni and Mn palmitates suggests good crystallinity for these soaps. The average planar distances i.e. long spacings obtained for Ni and Mn palmitates were 44.98 and 45.86 Å, for Ni laurate and stearate 33.80 and 48.80 Å and for Mn caproate, caprylate, caprate, laurate and myristate 21.5, 26.2, 28.9, 33.8 and 39.0 Å respectively. The differences in the long spacings for Ni/Mn homologous soaps correspond approximately to double the length of the methylene groups of soap molecules. However, the long spacings for Ni and Mn soaps are smaller than the calculated dimensions of anions (caproate, 22.0; caprylate, 27.0; caprate, 32.0; laurate, 37.0, myristate, 42.0; palmitate, 47.0; stearate, 52.0 Å) from Pauling's values of atomic radii and bond angles. The long spacings for Ni and Mn soaps are in agreement with the single layer structure of soaps proposed by Vold and Hattiangdi¹. The long spacings for homologous soaps suggest that there are no abrupt changes in the manner of crystallisation of Ni and Mn soaps. A number of peaks observed in the intermediate range of diffraction angles of 25–40° are attributed to the diffraction of X-rays by planes of atoms of much smaller separation than the basal planes. The calculated spacings from these peaks correspond to shorter side-spacings, i.e. lateral distance between one soap molecule and the next in a layer. It is found that the long spacing peaks are fairly intense while the short spacing peaks are relatively weak.

On the basis of long and short spacings, it is suggested that the metal ions are arranged in parallel planes equally spaced in the soap crystals with fully extended zig-zag chains of fatty acid radicals on both sides of each basal plane and these soaps possess single layer structure with molecular axes slightly inclined to the basal planes.

Thermal analysis : On heating Ni/Mn palmitate under normal atmospheric conditions, the weight of the final residue does not agree with the theoretical calculated weight of Ni/Mn oxide. This may be due to the fact that Ni palmitate decomposes to give a mixture of Ni and NiO and subse-

quently the metal also oxides to NiO at higher temperatures, while in case of decomposition of Mn palmitate, the oxide (MnO) oxidises to Mn₂O₃ and Mn₃O₄ at higher temperatures. It is found that a white powder condenses at the upper part of the sample tube and it is identified as palmitone (m.p. 82.8°).

The thermal decomposition of Ni and Mn palmitates under nitrogen atmosphere can be expressed as

(M = Ni or Mn)

The plots of the loss in weight w vs time t for Ni and Mn palmitates (figure not shown) are explained in terms following equations :

Freeman-Carroll equation² :

$$\frac{\Delta[\log(dw/dt)]}{\Delta[\log W_r]} = \frac{-E}{2.303R} \frac{\Delta[1/T]}{\Delta[\log W_r]} + n$$

Coats-Redfern equation³ for zero order reaction :

$$\log(\alpha/T^2) = \log \frac{AR}{aE} \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right] - \frac{E}{2.303RT}$$

Horowitz-Metzger equation⁴ :

$$\ln[\ln(1-\alpha)^{-1}] = \frac{E}{RT_s^2} (T - T_s) = \frac{E}{RT_s^2} \theta$$

where, E , R , T , n , W_r , (dw/dt) , α , A , a and T_s are energy of activation, gas constant, temperature (K), order of reaction, difference between the total loss and loss in weight at time (t), rate of weight-loss, fraction of soap decomposed, frequency factor, rate of heating (°C/min) and temperature (K) at which the rate of decomposition is maximum respectively.

The values of rate of weight loss, (dw/dt) were obtained from the plots of w vs t (figure not shown) and W_r were evaluated from the total loss in weight and loss at predetermined time. The plots of $\Delta[\log(dw/dt)]/\Delta[\log W_r]$ vs $\Delta(1/T)/\Delta(\log W_r)$ (Fig. 1) show that the order of decomposition reaction is zero and the energy of activation for the thermal decomposition of Ni and Mn palmitates is 13.7 kcal mol⁻¹. It is suggested that the surface of soap molecules remains covered by the molecules of gaseous product as the decomposition is fast and so the rate of decomposition becomes constant and the process is kinetically of zero or-

Fig. 1. Plots of $[\Delta(1/T)/\Delta(\log W_p)]$ vs $\Delta[\log(dw/dt)]/\Delta[\log(W_p)]$: (●) nickel palmitate and (▲) manganese palmitate.

der. The values of energy of activation calculated from the Coats-Redfern plots of $\log(\alpha/T^2)$ vs $(1/T)$ for Ni and Mn palmitates were found to be 10.1 and 16.5 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively, and that obtained from the Horowitz-Metzger plots of $\ln[\ln(1-\alpha)^{-1}]$ vs θ for Ni and Mn palmitates 15.9 and 12.2 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively. It is concluded that the decomposition reaction under nitrogen atmosphere is kinetically of zero order and the energy of activation for the process lies in the range 10–16 kcal mol⁻¹.

Infrared spectra: Ir spectra of palmitic acid and palmitates of Ni and Mn showed that the bands for the aliphatic portion of fatty acid molecule remained unchanged in the soap. The bands at 2 650, 1 700, 680 and 550 cm⁻¹ of palmitic acid are associated with the localised carboxyl group of the acid molecule in dimeric form involving hydrogen bonding. These bands disappeared completely in the spectra of Ni and Mn palmitates. The disappearance of the carbonyl band at 1 700 cm⁻¹ indicates that there may be a complete resonance in the two C–O bonds of carboxyl

group of soap molecule and the two C–O bonds become identical.

The appearance of bands of carboxylic group at 1 430–1 420 (sym.) and 1 570–1 560 cm⁻¹ (asym.) in the spectra of Ni and Mn palmitates instead of one band at 1 700 cm⁻¹ confirms ionic character of these soaps. The bands at 1 390–1 100 cm⁻¹ are assigned to the twisting and wagging vibrations of the chains of successive methylene groups of soap and acid molecules. The absence of 3 500–3 300 cm⁻¹ bands indicates the absence of coordinated water molecules in soap molecules. The bands at 480 and 450 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of Ni and Mn soaps correspond to Ni–O and Mn–O bonds respectively. The results are in agreement with the earlier report⁵.

The results show that the fatty acid exists with dimeric structure through intermolecular hydrogen bonding between carboxyl groups of two acid molecules whereas the metal-to-oxygen bonds in soaps are ionic in nature.

Electronic spectra: The solution spectra of Ni and Mn palmitates in methanol-benzene mixtures exhibit two bands (Ni : 14 705 and 25 641 cm⁻¹; Mn : 20 833 and 25 641 cm⁻¹). The electronic configuration of Ni^{II} under octahedral symmetry permits following three *d-d* spin allowed transitions : ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$. The first transition (at 8 000–10 000 cm⁻¹) could not be observed due to the limitation of our instrument. The bands at 14 705 and 25 641 cm⁻¹ correspond to the second and third transitions respectively. The value of crystal field splitting energy parameter (*Dq*) could not be obtained directly but was evaluated graphically⁶. The value of nephelauxetic ratio (β) was found to be 0.86 indicating that the metal-to-oxygen bond in Ni palmitate is not entirely ionic but is partly covalent in character. The value of Racah parameter (*B*, 892.7 cm⁻¹) is lower than that for free nickel ion and this lowering is the measure of covalency of metal-to-oxygen bond in the soap.

The two absorption maxima observed with solutions of Mn palmitate correspond to the following transitions : ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)$; ${}^4E_g(G)$ (this pair of transition is degenerated in octahedral geometry) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(D)$. The energy of these two transitions correspond to $10B + 5C$ and $17B + 5C$ respectively⁷ and provides a simple method of evaluating *B* and *C*. The value of interelectronic repulsion parameter for free Mn^{II} ion (*B₀*) is equal to 960 cm⁻¹. The value of β was found to be 0.72 indicating that the metal-to-oxygen bonds in Mn palmitate possess some covalent character.

The plots of optical density vs soap concentration at λ_{\max} for solutions of Ni and Mn palmitates in benzene-methanol mixture are linear for dilute soap solutions which proves the validity of Beer-Lambert's law. It is evident that

the spectrophotometric method can be used for estimation of Ni/Mn content in dilute solutions of soaps.

Experimental

Palmitic acid, benzene and methanol were purified by standard methods. Ni and Mn palmitates were prepared by metathesis of sodium palmitate with slight excess of aqueous solution of nickel sulphate/manganese acetate under vigorous stirring. The soaps were purified by crystallisation from benzene, dried and stored over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The X-ray diffraction patterns were recorded with a Rigaku (Geigerflex RB RU 200) instrument using CuK_α radiation filtered by a nickel foil over the range of diffraction angle of 5–60°. The readings of diffraction angle were made upto 0.01° and the wavelength of radiation was 1.542 Å. The TGA was carried out by a Stanton STA-780 thermal analyser at constant heating rate (10° min⁻¹). Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained with a Nicolet 50 X FT spectrophoto-

meter and electronic spectra with a Toshniwal CL 10 A3 spectrophotometer.

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